

WOMEN WRITERS IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Abstract; This paper focuses on the woman writers in the English literature and their strong writing as well. The most important women authors will be portrayed. The paper will also explore the economic, social, political and other circumstances that determined their writing and try to represent their lives, their agony, their struggles, their writing and the styles they used especially in essays that reach beyond a reading of a single text in order to challenge existing thinking or extend debates about an author, genre, topic, or theoretical viewpoint and relate literary analysis to wider cultural and intellectual contexts. Gender plays an important role in the lives of human beings. From the very first breath of their life, humans were taught to follow a strict code of behavior that differs depending on their sex. In a patriarchal society, this often means that a male will lead a dominated privileged life in which he has thought to be the standard for human experience and the female will lead a subordinate, submissive life in which she is defined only in relation to males. Both patriarchy and imperialism could be seen to exert different forms of domination over those subordinate to them. Because of this, it was important for the experiences of women under the patriarchal influence to come out to the forefront and reveal the undue cruelty be held on them by men. It was necessary for the women to protest against this male dominance over them. We observe that women continue to define the borders of the community, class and race. They tried to express their agony and dissatisfaction of male dominated attitudes through their works. Moreover , The view on the feminine issues depended on the economical and living conditions that women writers went through, their education, social environment, the attitude toward tradition and the issue of women's independence. Whether the starting point for readers is literary and cultural studies, critical theory, or the canon of literary writings and its traditions, the agendas that have now been argued by feminist theories and explored in women's writings, cannot now be silenced or suppressed. Yet we still inhabit a world in which the reality for many women is that they remain second-class citizens and many women suffer horrific violence and injustice. Therefore, there

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is still a crucial and immediate need to publish new scholarly critical work, which will help men and women to reconsider their past gender identities, and equally significant, to review their futures.

Keywords; novels, poems, publish, career, poet.

ЖЕНЩИНЫ-ПИСАТЕЛИ В АНГЛОЯЗЫЧНОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ

Абстрактный; В данной статье основное внимание уделяется женщинам-писателям в английской литературе, а также их сильным произведениям. Будут изображены наиболее важные женщины-писатели. В статье также будут исследованы экономические, социальные, политические и другие обстоятельства, которые определили их написание, и будет предпринята попытка отразить их жизнь, их агонию, их борьбу, их письмо и стили, которые они использовали, особенно в эссе, выходящих за рамки чтения одного текста. чтобы бросить вызов существующему мышлению или расширить дебаты об авторе, жанре, теме или теоретической точке зрения и связать литературный анализ с более широким культурным и интеллектуальным контекстом. Гендер играет важную роль в жизни людей. С самого первого вздоха жизни людей учили следовать строгому кодексу поведения, который различается в зависимости от пола. В патриархальном обществе это часто означает, что мужчина будет вести привилегированную жизнь, в которой он считает себя стандартом человеческого опыта, а женщина будет вести подчиненную, покорную жизнь, в которой она определяется только по отношению к мужчинам. Можно рассматривать как патриархат, так и империализм в различных формах господства над теми, кто им подчиняется. В связи с этим мне было важно, чтобы переживания женщин, находящихся под патриархальным влиянием, вышли на первый план и выявили неоправданную жестокость, предъявляемую к ним со стороны меня. Женщинам было необходимо протестовать против этого мужского доминирования над ними. Мы наблюдаем, что женщины продолжают определять границы сообщества, класса и расы. В своих работах они пытались выразить свою агонию и недовольство отношением, в котором доминируют мужчины. При этом взгляд на женскую проблематику зависел от экономических и жизненных условий, в которых оказались женщины-писательницы, их образования, социального окружения, отношения к традициям и вопросу женской независимости.

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Независимо от того, являются ли отправной точкой для читателей литературные и культурные исследования, критическая теория или канон литературных произведений и их традиций, программы, которые сейчас аргументируются феминистскими теориями и исследуются в женских произведениях, теперь не могут быть замалчиваемы или подавлены. Тем не менее, мы по-прежнему живем в мире, в котором реальность для многих женщин такова, что они остаются гражданами второго сорта, и многие женщины страдают от ужасающего насилия и несправедливости. Таким образом, по-прежнему существует острая и неотложная необходимость публикации новых научных критических работ, которые помогут мужчинам и женщинам пересмотреть свою прошлую гендерную идентичность и, что не менее важно, пересмотреть свое будущее.

Ключевые слова; романы, стихи, публикации, карьера, поэт.

INTRODUCTION; KIA ABDULLAH

Kia Abdullah (born 17 May 1982) is a British writer and traveller. His most famous works are *Take It Back*, *Truth Be Told*, and *Next of Kin*, and he is the best-selling author of these dramas. *The New York Times*, *The Guardian*, *The Times*, *The Financial Times*, *The Telegraph* and *BBC* and other publications also published samples of creativity. Abdullah graduated in 2003, after which he worked in the technology sector for three years. In 2007, he quit his tech job to pursue a career as a writer. After that, his salary will be reduced by 50%. From 2008 to 2010, Abdullah wrote a series of articles for *The Guardian* on a range of topics from politics to relationships. She has also worked as an interviewer for *Asian Woman* magazine, during which time she has interviewed prominent Asian actors and musicians such as Riz Ahmed, Meera Syal, Nitin Sawhney, Jay Sean and Anushka Shankar. Abdullah has been an occasional guest on *BBC Radio 2's Jeremy Vine Show* and the *BBC Asian Network's DJ Nihal Show*, speaking candidly about drug use and gender inequality. In 2009, he was nominated for the *Muslim Writers Award*. In 2011, he became embroiled in a *Twitter* controversy. In 2012, he joined global publisher *Penguin Random House*, where he worked on *Rough Guides'* travel brand. In 2014, Abdullah quit his job and started *Atlas & Boots*, an outdoor travel blog with 250,000 monthly readers. Abdullah has contributed to *Lonely Planet* and *Rough Guides* and has been interviewed about his travels on television, radio, print and online. In 2019, Abdullah was highly acclaimed by *The Guardian*, *The Telegraph* and *The Sunday Times* for crime and thrillers.

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published *Take It Back* as one of his shortlisted novels. In 2020, he founded Asian Booklist, a website that helps readers discover new books by British-Asian authors. Abdullah's second novel, *Truth Be Told*, was published by HarperCollins in 2020 shortlisted for the Diverse Book Award. His third novel, *Next of Kin*, was named The Times Book of the Month and his fourth novel, *Hose People Door* is scheduled to be published in 2023.

Lilias Armstrong

Lilias Eveline Armstrong (29 September 1882, Pendlebury, Lancashire, England - 9 December 1937, North Finchley, Middlesex, United Kingdom) was an English phonetician. During his tenure at University College London, he attained the rank of Reader. Armstrong is best known for his work on intonation in English, as well as phonetics and intonation in Somali and Kikuyu. His book on English intonation, co-written with Ida C. Ward, has been published continuously for 50 years. He is also considered one of the first scholars to work on detailed descriptions of tone in the Somali and Kikuyu languages. Armstrong grew up in Northern England. He graduated from the University of Leeds with a BA. There he studied French and Latin. For some time he taught French at a primary school in the suburbs of London. However, later, under the leadership of Daniel Jones, he began working at the Department of Phonetics at University College London. Notable works include *A Handbook of English Intonation*, co-authored with Ward in 1926, *The Phonetic Structure of Somalia*, published in 1934, and posthumously (1937, at the age of 55, due to a stroke), was the author of *The Phonetic and Tonal Structure of Kikuyu*, published in 1940. For more than ten years, he has been the editor of *Le Maître Phonétique*, a journal of the International Phonetic Association. During his career, he received many accolades for teaching during the summer holidays in addition to the academic period. In his obituary, Jones noted that Armstrong was "one of the best phoneticians in the world."

Armstrong first taught phonetics in 1917 at Daniel Jones' missionary summer course. Prior to this, Jones had planned to appoint him to a full-time position in the phonetics department at University College London. Jones' plans were temporarily put on hold when London County Council decided against increasing the department's budget in October. However, in November 1917, Armstrong was nominated for a temporary (officially in February 1918), part-time lecturer position.

Selected works

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Charlotte Brontë

Charlotte Bronte (April 21, 1816 - March 31, 1855) was a famous English writer and poet, the eldest of the three Bronte sisters who survived to adulthood, an English writer whose novels have become classics of English literature. Charlotte Brontë was born on 21 April 1816 in Market Street, Thornton, west of Bradford in the West Riding of Yorkshire. Third child of Irish Anglican priest Maria (Branwell) and Patrick Bronte (née Brunty). In 1820, his family moved to the village of Haworth, where his father was appointed curate of St. Michael and All Angels. Maria died of cancer on 15 September 1821, leaving five daughters, Maria, Elizabeth, Charlotte, Emily and Anna, and a son, Branwell, to be cared for by her sister Elizabeth Branwell. In August 1824, Patrick sent his daughters Charlotte, Emily, Maria and Elizabeth to the Clergy's Daughters' School, near Cowan Bridge in Lancashire. Charlotte claimed that the poor conditions at the school had a lasting effect on her health and physical development, and in June 1825 Maria (b. 1814) and Elizabeth (b. 1815) died of tuberculosis. After the death of his older daughters, Patrick decides to withdraw Charlotte and Emily from school. From 1831 to 1832, Brontë continued her education at Roe Head School in Mirfield, where she met her best friends Ellen Nussey and Mary Taylor. In 1833, he wrote the novel "The Green Dwarf" using the name Wellesley. From about 1833, he switched from supernatural

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tales to writing realistic stories. He worked as a teacher at Roe Head from 1835 to 1838. Unhappy and lonely as a teacher at Roe Head, Brontë turned her sorrows into poetry and wrote a series of melancholy poems. In *We wove a Web in Childhood*, written in December 1835, Brontë tries to reflect her hard life as a teacher. Many of his poems dealt with the fictional world of Angria, often with Byronic characters, and in December 1836 he wrote to the poet Robert Southey, asking him to encourage his career as a poet. Southey famously replied: "Literature cannot and should not be the main work of a woman's life. The more busy he is with his duties, the less time he has for accomplishments and leisure." He respected this advice but ignored it. In 1839-1841, he was hired as a tutor to several families in Yorkshire and taught their children. In particular, from May to July 1839, he was employed by the Sidgwick family at Stone Gape, a summer residence in Lothersdale. But Bronte is not satisfied with her work as a teacher, because her employers treat her almost like a slave and constantly humiliate her. In May 1846, Charlotte, Emily and Anne self-financed the publication of a joint collection of poems under their names Currer, Ellis and Acton Bell. The pseudonyms retain the sisters' initials and hide their gender; So was Charlotte Currer Bell.

Novels

Jane Eyre, published in 1847

Shirley, published in 1849

Villette, published in 1853

Emma, unfinished; Brontë wrote only 20 pages of the manuscript, which was published posthumously in 1860. At least two sequels to this passage have appeared in recent decades

Emma, Charlotte Bronte and the Other Lady, published in 1980; Although it is attributed to Elizabeth Goudge, the real author was Constance Savery.

Emma Brown, this work by Claire Boylan, was published in 2003

Poetry

Currer, Ellis and Acton Bell Poems 1846

Selected Poems of the Brontës, Everyman's Poetry 1997

Agatha Christie

English writer Agatha Christie (1890-1976) is one of the most widely read writers in the world, and her works have been published in more than four billion copies in more than one hundred languages. His books rank third in the West after the Bible

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and Shakespeare. Agatha Christie is the author of more than 60 detective novels, 6 psychological novels, 19 short story collections and 16 plays. At that time, not many people heard the name Agatha Christie. Afraid that detective fans would not buy books written by female writers, Agatha Christie invented a male pseudonym for herself. These were the nicknames "Mart West", "Martin Gray", "Westmacott". But the writer became famous with her first name (Agata) and the last name of her first husband (Christy). Her real name was Agatha Mary Clarissa Miller. After the infidelity of her first husband, Agatha Christie's marriage broke up, and she later married a second time and became Agatha Mallowen. He wrote his psychological novels under the name "Westmacott". Because Agatha Christie did not like to write, she had many of her novels written orally. A person usually comes up with new ideas during light physical activities, such as walking, hiking, traveling, or during idle meditation. Agatha Christie came up with unusual enigmatic stories while washing dishes. During the First World War, Agatha Christie worked as a nurse in a hospital. Later, he also worked in the field of pharmaceuticals. For this reason, in most detective works, characters are killed by poisons. Agatha Christie's second husband was an archaeologist. The writer traveled with him to many countries, in particular to Syria, Iraq, and Turkey. He wrote one of his famous works, the novel "Murder on the Orient Express" in a hotel in Istanbul. Agatha Christie's most famous work is "Ten Negro Children", and because the word "Negro" is an insult in America, the word "Hindu" was used in its publication there. When a mini-series based on the novel "Ten Negro Children" was filmed in the UK, the mini-series was called "No One Left". In 1926, Agatha Christie disappeared without a trace. Only his coat was found in his car. No letter was left, and there were no signs of abduction. In addition to police officers and enthusiasts, dozens of volunteers were looking for him. Even the famous detective writer Arthur Conan Doyle, the author of Sherlock Holmes stories, was looking for it. This happened when Agatha Christie's husband was unfaithful. Ten days later, the police found Agatha Christie in one of the hotels. She wanted to disappear after her husband's betrayal and, interestingly, she registered in that hotel with the name and surname of her husband's lover. It was known that Arthur Conan Doyle took his photo to a fortune teller when he did not find it. Agatha Christie died of a cold on January 12, 1976 at the age of 85. He was buried in St. Mary's Cemetery in Cholsey, Oxfordshire, England. Agatha Christie concluded her

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autobiographical work with the following sentence: "I thank you, Lord, for the wonderful life and all the love you have given me."

Agatha Christie's books

The Mysterious Affair at Styles

The Big Four

The Murder on the Links

The Secret of Chimneys

The Murder of Roger Ackroyd

The Mystery of the Blue Train

The Secret Adversary

The Sittaford Mystery

The Man in the Brown Suit

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